

Improved compression of SAR matrices by a reformulation of the generalized virtual observation point compression scheme

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Summary of Main Findings: The Virtual Observation Points compression problem is reformulated to further reduce by a factor ~ 5 the number of SAR matrices used for RF pulse design and exam supervision.

Synopsis: Parallel transmission to date is the most promising technology to tackle the RF field inhomogeneity problem in MRI at ultra-high field. The Virtual Observation Point compression technique was a cornerstone in the field to reduce drastically the number of SAR matrices to handle in exam supervision and RF pulse design. After its original discovery, it was further improved to boost the compression. This work describes a reformulation of the problem which simplifies substantially the numerical search and allows reducing further the number of matrices by a factor ~ 5 or more.

Introduction: The lack of one-to-one mapping between RF power and the specific absorption rate (SAR) warrants handling SAR constraints explicitly^{1,2} in RF pulse design and exam supervision. Within that context, the Virtual Observation Point (VOP)³ approach was a cornerstone to reduce drastically the number of SAR matrices and make explicit SAR handling tractable. The initial approach³ guaranteed that the SAR at one voxel location with some overestimation would be upper-bounded by the one at another location for every RF pulse. Lee et al⁴ further extended the idea by performing an optimization based on the observation that the SAR at one location could be upper-bounded by different VOPs depending on the RF pulse. The problem for the latter yet is the size of the optimization problem growing with the number of VOPs, which makes the implementation time-consuming and the results more uncertain, given the non-convexity of the problem. Here the generalized VOP scheme is reformulated to obtain a fixed number of optimization variables at each iteration of the compression algorithm, which is shown to boost compression rate.

Methods: Let Q_i be SAR matrices in W/kg ($i=1\dots N$ for the number of voxels), and b a 8×1 complex vector of modulus 1 representing a normalized RF pulse for a 8-Tx array. The Q matrices are sorted in descending order according to their maximum eigenvalues. The first one is retained as the first VOP and is called Q_{VOP-1} . In Eichfelder's method, the second one, Q_2 , is retained as a VOP if and only if for $\forall b \in \mathbb{C}^8$, $b^\dagger Q_{VOP-1} b + \lambda b^\dagger Q_G b \geq b^\dagger Q_2 b$, where λ is a scalar controlling the overestimation and Q_G is an Hermitian matrix (here taken as the global SAR matrix). If $Q_{VOP-1} + \lambda Q_G - Q_2$ is positive semidefinite (all eigenvalues larger than or equal to 0) (psd), the inequality is true, Q_2 is upper-bounded and should not be added to the VOP list. It is added otherwise and the process continues with the next voxel SAR matrix. The generalized approach consists of verifying a sufficient, but not necessary, condition whereby a linear combination of VOPs upper-bounds a current Q_k VOP candidate⁴. Let $C_{i=1\dots NVOPS}$ be the optimization coefficients for the current list of VOPs. It boils down to: if there exists $(C_1, \dots, C_{NVOPS}) \in \mathbb{R}^+$ such that $\sum_i^{NVOPS} C_i = 1$ and $\sum_i^{NVOPS} C_i Q_i + \lambda Q_G - Q_k$ psd, then Q_k is upper-bounded and is not retained. Otherwise, Q_k is added to the list of VOPs etc... We now implement here instead the reverse: a VOP candidate Q_k is not upper-bounded if we can find $b \in \mathbb{C}^8$ / $b^\dagger Q_k b > \max_{i=1\dots NVOPS} (b^\dagger (Q_i + \lambda Q_G) b)$. If such a b vector can be found, then Q_k is kept as VOP. The problem thus can be formulated as: $\min_b f(b) = \max_{i=1\dots NVOPS} (b^\dagger (Q_i + \lambda Q_G - Q_k) b)$, s.t. $\|b\| = 1$, the sign of $f(b)$ after optimization determining the fate of Q_k (VOP or not). The number of variables hence remains 2 times the number of channels, instead of hundreds or more in the generalized approach (the $C_{i=1\dots NVOPS}$ coefficients), regardless of the number of VOPs. The procedure was tested using electromagnetic simulations of the Nova (Nova medical, Wilmington, MA, USA) 8Tx-32Rx coil provided by the coil manufacturer and run on the Duke head model. Around 110 000 SAR-Q matrices were computed and averaged over 10g of contiguous tissue at 4 mm isotropic resolution. The proposed compression was implemented in Matlab (Mathworks, Natick, MA, USA) using the active-set approach available with the `fmincon` function, with 5 initial random seeds. It was compared with Lee's generalized approach⁴ for an interval of λ ranging from 0.7 to 1.5. After compression, 10^6 random RF shims were generated and the true peak SAR value among all voxels versus the values obtained with the different compressed sets were calculated.

Results: Fig. 1 reports the number of VOPs for each value of λ . At $\lambda=0.7$, the numbers of VOPs are 938 and 147 respectively for Lee's generalized⁴ approach and the proposed one. Increasing the number of seeds further did not change the number of VOPs, suggesting convergence. Fig. 2 shows the true SAR versus the compressed one calculated with the two methods and for 10^6 random RF shims. SAR is never underestimated.

Discussion and conclusion: A method to further compress SAR matrices with VOPs was proposed. One important difference with the generalized approach⁴ is the number of optimization variables remaining constant throughout the process, i.e. not scaling with the number of VOPs. Although the mathematical problem is well-posed, our results constitute for the moment strong numerical evidence but no proof for bounding. Not finding b such that $f(b) < 0$ indeed does not imply that such b does not exist.

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References: [1] A. Hoyos-Idrobo et al. *IEEE TMI* 33:739-748 (2014) [2] B. Guérin et al. *Magn. Reson. Med.* 71:1446-1457 (2014). [3] G. Eichfelder and M. Gebhardt. *Magn. Reson. Med.* 66:1468-1476 (2011). [4] J. Lee et al. *Magn. Reson. Med.* 67:1566-1578 (2012).

Figure 1. Number of VOPs computed for different overestimation factors λ . Blue: Lee's generalized VOP compression method, red: this work.

Figure 2. 10g-SAR computed over the uncompressed set of voxels and over the VOPs for the two different methods ($\lambda=0.7$) and for 1 million random RF shims. a) 10g-SAR over the VOPs versus the true SAR. The dashed black line is the identity line. b) Boxplots of the relative overestimation for the two methods. The SAR is never underestimated.